

An Overview on Good Health & Wellness in the Divine Light of Shrimad Bhagavad Gita

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1.Abstract

The Bhagavad Gita is the supreme most spiritual classic India has given to the world .It is not just a religious text but its also a beacon of light for health and happy living a kind of a “Good Health Life manual”. The divine interaction of Lord Krishna and Arjuna on the battle of Kurukshetra on the verge of the war gives deeper insights on various aspects of life management including good health, wellness, and fitness and leading a life to the fullest and with the help of good health move Godwards. Our body and health is a medium to reach God and should be treated with greater care . The Great dietician Padmashree Dr KK Agarwal mentions Lord Krishna to be the first “Psychologist” & “ Counselor “ who through the Gita teaches Arjuna and the mankind the various tips of maintaining a balanced mind, body and soul consciousness. This research paper throws light on multiple aspects, factors of good health and the divine tips Lord Krishna has given us to achieve our objective of Healthy Mind & Healthy Body & further reach our Final Spiritual Goal of life.

2.Keywords

Lord Krishna, Bhagavad Gita, Health, Wellness, Mental Health, Fitness, Human Psychology, Counselor, Diet

3.Introduction

The teaching of the Upanishads is ‘*Sharir Madhyam Khalu Dharmasadhan*’, If the Body is healthy and fit it will become a strong medium to achieve your dharma, your objectives in Life and becomes dispeller of grief in life ! The Bhagavad Gita is the divine conversation between Krishna and Arjuna Most of us treat Gita as a religious book only but actually the Gita the divine song is much beyond religion. Once A human being is born there are lot many challenges in life. In our life due to multiple challenges we get lot of tension, stress, anxiety ,worry ,fear and this further results into multiple physical, mental and psychological problems, complications and issues which again leads to lot of wastage of resources and especially waste of money. The Gita emphasizes on Simple Living and High Thinking and stands as a High Profile Health Care

Manual and also a Manual of Holistic Well Being ..It teaches three things: “*Brahma – Vidyayam*” *Yoga- shastre Shrikrishnaarjuna-samvade*”. It means Theory, Practice, and Realization. This theory can indeed help in coping up the stress arising from day to day challenges of life. It is “Brahmavidya” and also a shastra of Yoga !

4. Objectives of the Study

The research paper on “Gita –Health & Wellness” is aimed to address the following objectives as follows:

1. To know the Importance , Teachings of Gita & find the divine keys for developing Good Health & Wellness.
2. To study, analyze, understand the problems related to human health and derive the solutions provided in the Lessons of Gita for the working professionals in today’s modern era.
3. To discover the various attributes of the Gita for developing good health in order to achieve our Life goals & Professional goals and uplift our mind,body & soul.

5. Need for the Research

The following research study was conducted as it was found that there is a huge gap in research and understanding about Gita being a Manual for Good Health and Wellness..An extensive exploration has been carried out and derivatives has been carried in the field of Gita and the Management perspectives for the Corporates But there is no much deep study carried out studying the indepth analysis of Gita as a torch bearer and light bearer of human health. In today’s contemporary era with the globe struggling out post covid pandemic scenario it has become the need of the hour to do a deep research and seek insights and divine guidelines of the holy Gita for not just the youth but for all ages and classes . In this 21st century due to the changing times there are a lot of mental and behavioral issues in the world and the teachings of Lord Krishna in form of the directives in the Bhagavad Gita are like a bright sunshine in the darkness.

6. Research Methodology

The research is completely Exploratory and Descriptive in nature. The research focuses on Literature review in Research papers, Journals, News Papers, and Magazines, Books, websites, weblinks and all other authentic and amicable sources. The study attempts to analyze the status of Health & Wellness of Executives in the Corporate world and tries to derive whether they are following the teachings of Gita with regards to Health & Wellness in Mumbai and Navi Mumbai location. The Data collection was made through a well defined structured questionnaire based on a Likert scale of 1 to 5 points. The sample size of the population is 145 and SPSS has been used for calculations and data analysis. The total number of questions is 36 with multiple choices.

Researcher also tested following hypothesis in the context of given research . We also tested hypothesis with the help of t-test. It is observed that p-value is 0.000. Hence null hypothesis H₀ is rejected and the alternative hypothesis H₁ is accepted, which means the Teachings of the Bhagavad Gita do contribute a lot in developing Good Health and Wellness for the Human Capital . The Bhagavad Gita learnings if implemented can play significant role in developing good physical and mental health and getting solutions to the related problems.

H₀ : Shrimad Bhagavad Gita Teachings do not contribute in developing Good health & wellness nor provides solutions to related problems of Working Executives.

H₁ : Shrimad Bhagavad Gita Teachings contribute in developing Good health & wellness & provides solutions to related problems of Working Executives.

7. Literature Review

The Literature Review of the past researches, studies and papers is absolutely essential and has proved highly helpful in the present study. The previous research gives a clear picture of the analysis, reviews and evaluations done till date and also helped in setting the context of the future research and most importantly identifies the gap and the need and scope of current research. The Literature review has highly helped in the existing research which is based on authentic references.

Stress management and coping embedded in the Bhagavad Gita Nidhi Verma & Ajay Singh 2014 explains in their paper that people are living lives full of stress due to multiple reasons in life and have got into various psychological related issues. To treat the same there are various therapies. Our most ancient spiritual book is the Bhagavad Gita in which Lord Krishna speaks to Arjuna for removing all the worries, dilemmas and anxieties of life . As on today in the modern world the Gita helps in solving day to day problems and also prevents us from the stress arising out of these issues & emphasizing Gita as an effective tool of management to remove stress and achieve work excellence.

Cognitive Behaviour Therapy in Perspective of the Bhagavad Gita Neha Sharma 2014 in her paper describes that the Bhagavad Gita offers a priceless content on Cognitive Behaviour therapy as Lord Krishna removed the cognitive distortions from Arjuna's mind and made him ready to fight the battle. Here Krishna doesn't act just as a Leader but he also acts as a therapist ! who removes Arjuna's stress and makes him mentally fit and fine. There are both positive and negative patterns of the mind and its behavior with different emotions, attitudes and beliefs. At many times Cognitive behavior therapies have failed but the Gita model of CBT is much effective and highly result oriented. Trust, devotion and complete surrender of patient towards the therapist as done by The Arjuna and emphasis on work with renunciation (Karma Yoga) by The Krishna made CBT more effective and efficient in delivering fair result.

Mental health in Bhagavad Gita B V Pattabhiram* & Balaji Deekshitulu P V 2017 in their paper suggests that management of self, mind and duty are the key aspects in Bhagavad Gita which also help in character building and success in work . Additionally the Gita is full of treasure to increase mind management and reduce all sorts of psycho and mental disorders. The papers explores and discusses such divine teachings to manage mind and develop the human resources to achieve work excellence .

Psychotherapy - Insights from Bhagavad Gita M. S. Reddy 2012 in his paper discusses the important lessons of psychotherapy and solutions to cognitive problems offered by the Gita quoting the reference of Mahatma Gandhi who said that whenever he had problems he referred to Gita for solutions.Gita gives us lessons in conflict resolutions , getting rid of anxiety,coming out of depression and inaction and comes out with a therapies which Lord Krishna used to help Arjuna. The focus of the Gita is on diagnosis of patient and the Guru Shishya concept.

Building resilience in the COVID-19 era: Three paths in the Bhagavad Gita Matcheri S. Keshavan 2020 in his paper systematically presented thought that Bhagavad Gita has a treasure of wealth which helps in overcoming psychological issues for those affected in the covid pandemic by understanding and learning the path of Karma Yoga ,Gyan Yoga & Raja Yoga which helps the Patients, Doctors and Frontline health workers providing them care and improves their spirit to face the issues of illness and its consequences and come out of the pandemic .In addition there is further more scope for empirical study.

Coping with Illness: Insight from the Bhagavad Gita Bharti Kalra et al August 2018 in their paper explains how to cope up with various situations in life with the help of enlightening Bhagavad Gita and by addressing demanding situations. The divine discourse between Krishna and Arjuna is a clear instrument of getting rid from illness to wellness and helps us even removing chronic health issues like diabetes by making changes in day to day activities, diet & exercise.

Bhagavad Gita as a text of counselling- A methodical study with the association of counselling and Psychotherapeutic techniques 2021 Main Authors- Deepshikha Thakur et al in their paper discovers a key fact that the holy Bhagavad Gita is a not only a spiritual scripture but also a bigger text of counseling whos dimensions can be scientifically co-related. The Dialouge between Lord Krishna and Arjuna is divine and consists of counseling techniques and psychotherapies

Bhagavad Gita Sheth HC. Bhagavad Gita 2021 in his paper performed a conceptualization that Bhagavad Gita teaches us to achieve good physical and mental health. It throws light on how one should have a good diet and how it can have a good impact on human behavior. In modern science its difficult to find such a classification of linkage but Gita teachings relate to human behavioral patterns. Along with medication for physical and mental health the regulation of diet has also become a most important factor for removing various ailments.

COVID-19, Moral Injury and the Bhagavad Gita Bindu Menon et al 2021 in their paper presents a comparative analysis on Covid 19, Moral Injury and the Gita. The Spiritual practices and advice may help to deal with demotivation and removing moral distress on the basis of the divine dialogue of Krishna to Arjuna which can be capsuled in form of 4Ds – Detachment, Duty, Do-ership and Dhyana. The paper should explore how these concepts are useful aids to minimize demoralization and distress.

Satwajayaka Chikitsa in Bhagavad Gita Shrinibash et al 2020 World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research. in his paper states that the Gita provides the 4 yogas is actually “Satwajayaka Chikitsa” which helps in elimination of depressive thoughts, confidence building, boosting motivation and upliftment of Satva which leads to happy life free from all diseases and gets mukti in life. There are psychotherapeutic interventions in the Gita which can be used as models for the treatment of patients who are mentally challenged.

Teachings of Bhagavad Gita in dealing with stress during Pandemic times (Covid -19) A Perspective Sakshi Vermani & SanGita Chauhan 2020 in their paper states that during the covid pandemic everyones life went into a tizzy and we had to face altogether different situation which lead to challenges like increase in mental health issues like anxiety, dilemma, depression and nervousness. The Bhagavad Gita and its divine teachings came to us as a sunlight in the darkness helping us to cope up with all the negativities and as a long run solution to our problems. The researchers present a thought of that the Holy Bhagavad Gita is a spiritual text which helps us to face, cope and come out of challenging situations & come out of the same especially in stressful pandemic.

8. Data Analysis & Interpretation

The Statistical analysis and calculations of the responses of the survey questionnaire was done through SPSS. The following are results and findings stated in form of the tables.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.804	.842	36

The above table shows Reliability statistics for the given variables with the help of Cronbach’s Alpha test. It is observed that the given value is 0.804 hence it shows **Good Level for Internal Consistency.**

KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.	.859
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square df Sig.
	2639.470 630 .000

The Above table shows result of KMO and Bartlett's Tests. The Sampling adequacy value is **0.859** which shows **Meritorious Level towards sampling Adequacy**. Significance value is 0.000 which shows The significant value less than 0.05 indicates that **these data do not produce an identity matrix and are thus approximately multivariate normal and acceptable for further analysis.**

Table No-1**Descriptive Statistics**

Descriptive Statistics							
Variable	Mean	Std Dev.	Std Err	N	Z	DF	P
I am aware that the Holy Gita is a Health Manual	3.972	0.971	0.081	145	49.241	144	0.000
I know that Lord Krishna is a Psychologist & Counselor	3.317	1.159	0.096	145	34.467	144	0.000
I have complete Self Awareness about my Health Status	3.766	1.007	0.084	145	45.027	144	0.000
I have understanding about the 3 types of foods	3.338	1.215	0.101	145	33.092	144	0.000
My Food affects my Health	2.007	1.115	0.093	145	21.676	144	0.000
My Food affects my concentration	2.434	1.195	0.099	145	24.532	144	0.000
My Food affects my Studies & Office work	2.331	1.259	0.105	145	22.302	144	0.000
Satvik Food is the best for life	3.862	0.955	0.079	145	48.714	144	0.000
I Understand the real meaning of Fasting & its not about only food but controlling the senses	2.724	1.115	0.093	145	29.425	144	0.000

Fasting of Food is essential for my my good health	2.179	1.134	0.094	145	23.131	144	0.000
I have complete control over Anger	2.207	1.092	0.091	145	24.330	144	0.000
Anger affects my health	3.510	1.094	0.091	145	38.650	144	0.000
I have complete control over Lust	3.897	0.895	0.074	145	52.402	144	0.000
Lust adversely affects my life	3.586	1.245	0.103	145	34.688	144	0.000
I have a lot of Greed in my Life	2.179	1.153	0.096	145	22.766	144	0.000
Greed leads to tension and jealousy	4.269	0.729	0.061	145	70.523	144	0.000
Mental Stress affects my Personal life	2.283	1.110	0.092	145	24.765	144	0.000
Yoga & Pranayam helps me to improve life	3.834	1.000	0.083	145	46.169	144	0.000
I do Pranayam regularly	3.759	0.974	0.081	145	46.478	144	0.000
My Sleeping schedule is very balanced	3.524	1.161	0.096	145	36.545	144	0.000
Gymming helps me for Healthy Life	3.676	0.964	0.080	145	45.925	144	0.000
I do workout regularly	4.028	0.935	0.078	145	51.870	144	0.000
I do believe Connecting to myself	3.862	0.895	0.074	145	51.985	144	0.000
Meditation helps me in being calm and peaceful	4.048	0.892	0.074	145	54.629	144	0.000
I have Fear & Anxiety of future life	4.248	0.812	0.067	145	62.961	144	0.000
I have fear of death	4.193	0.766	0.064	145	65.877	144	0.000
I keep on thinking of Past-Present & Future	4.214	0.756	0.063	145	67.088	144	0.000
My Devotion helps me in Good Mental Health	4.269	0.729	0.061	145	70.523	144	0.000
Chanting helps positively in my Life	3.972	0.957	0.079	145	49.982	144	0.000
I am detached which helps me in my FOCUS	3.862	0.940	0.078	145	49.473	144	0.000
I believe in Spiritual Healing Thearapies are of great use	4.007	0.837	0.070	145	57.614	144	0.000
I trust Doctor whom I seek treatment	4.034	0.837	0.069	145	58.058	144	0.000
Positiving Thinking is a good medicine of the mind	3.917	0.886	0.074	145	53.247	144	0.000

I believe in being Myself and don't get stressed comparing life with others	3.993	0.804	0.067	145	59.834	144	0.000
Self Confidence helps as boost to my Good health	4.076	0.782	0.065	145	62.724	144	0.000
Shift in our mindset towards our Spirituality helps in Good Health & Wellness	4.007	0.821	0.068	145	58.790	144	0.000

Table No-1 shows that descriptive statistics with the help of Mean, standard deviation and standard error. Researcher has checked the central tendency of given attributes of role of Gita in development of various attributes related to health and wellness. It is observed that mean value, standard deviation and standard error shows significant relationship among the various attributes of Shrimad Bhagavad Gita and Health & Wellness .

Table No-2
Communalities

Communalities		
Variable	Initial	Final
I am aware that the Holy Gita is a Health Manual	1.000	0.366
I know that Lord Krishna is a Psychologist & Counselor	1.000	0.335
I have complete Self Awareness about my Health Status	1.000	0.278
I have understanding about the 3 types of foods	1.000	0.314
My Food affects my Health	1.000	0.454
My Food affects my concentration	1.000	0.533
My Food affects my Studies & Office work	1.000	0.448
Satvik Food is the best for life	1.000	0.336
I Understand the real meaning of Fasting & its not about only food but controlling the senses	1.000	0.405
Fasting of Food is essential for my my good health	1.000	0.480
I have complete control over Anger	1.000	0.479
Anger affects my health	1.000	0.324
I have complete control over Lust	1.000	0.519
Lust adversely affects my life	1.000	0.368
I have a lot of Greed in my Life	1.000	0.365
Greed leads to tension and jealousy	1.000	0.475
Mental Stress affects my Personal life	1.000	0.286
Yoga & Pranayam helps me to improve life	1.000	0.345
I do Pranayam regularly	1.000	0.364
My Sleeping schedule is very balanced	1.000	0.269

Gymming helps me for Healthy Life	1.000	0.319
I do workout regularly	1.000	0.487
I do believe Connecting to myself	1.000	0.441
Meditation helps me in being calm and peaceful	1.000	0.302
I have Fear & Anxiety of future life	1.000	0.621
I have fear of death	1.000	0.665
I keep on thinking of Past-Present & Future	1.000	0.633
My Devotion helps me in Good Mental Health	1.000	0.629
Chanting helps positively in my Life	1.000	0.403
I am detached which helps me in my FOCUS	1.000	0.621
I believe in Spiritual Healing Therapies are of great use	1.000	0.466
I trust Doctor whom I seek treatment	1.000	0.429
Positive Thinking is a good medicine of the mind	1.000	0.504
I believe in being Myself and don't get stressed comparing life with others	1.000	0.526
Self Confidence helps as boost to my Good health	1.000	0.470
Shift in our mindset towards our Spirituality helps in Good Health & Wellness	1.000	0.610

Table No-2 shows communalities among the variables considered for the Study. It is observed that all initial communalities for all variables are 1.000 and final communalities for all variables are 0.2 to 0.9. From the correlation matrix there is high degree of correlation matrix among the variables considered for the study. It is observed that there is a positive co-relation between following Shrimad Bhagavad Gita for Good Health & wellness.

Table No-3
Eigen Value

	Factor 1	Factor 2	Factor 3	Factor 4	Factor 5	Factor 6	Factor 7	Factor 8	Factor 9	Factor 10
Value	10.702	3.307	1.860	1.851	1.481	1.267	1.184	1.093	1.059	1.009
% of Var.	29.728	9.187	5.167	5.141	4.114	3.520	3.289	3.035	2.941	2.804
Cum. %	29.728	38.914	44.081	49.222	53.337	56.857	60.146	63.181	66.122	68.926
	Factor 11	Factor 12	Factor 13	Factor 14	Factor 15	Factor 16	Factor 17	Factor 18	Factor 19	Factor 20
Value	0.934	0.857	0.821	0.760	0.736	0.629	0.591	0.555	0.503	0.461
% of Var.	2.594	2.381	2.280	2.112	2.045	1.748	1.641	1.542	1.397	1.280
Cum. %	71.520	73.901	76.181	78.293	80.339	82.087	83.728	85.270	86.667	87.947

	Factor 21	Factor 22	Factor 23	Factor 24	Factor 25	Factor 26	Factor 27	Factor 28	Factor 29	Factor 30
Value	0.434	0.410	0.381	0.350	0.340	0.327	0.295	0.259	0.239	0.233
% of Var.	1.207	1.138	1.058	0.973	0.943	0.909	0.819	0.718	0.663	0.647
Cum. %	89.153	90.291	91.349	92.322	93.265	94.174	94.994	95.712	96.375	97.021
	Factor 31	Factor 32	Factor 33	Factor 34	Factor 35	Factor 36				
Value	0.231	0.206	0.191	0.159	0.151	0.135				
% of Var.	0.642	0.571	0.532	0.442	0.418	0.374				
Cum. %	97.663	98.234	98.766	99.208	99.626	100.000				

Table No-4
Sum of Squared Loadings

Extraction Explained Variance (Sum of Squared Loadings)			
	Factor 1	Factor 2	Factor 3
Value	10.702	3.307	1.860
% of Var.	29.728	9.187	5.167
Cum. %	29.728	38.914	44.081

Table No-3 and Table no-4 shows representation of Eigen values. It is observed that factor one contributes 29.72% variance in the given factor analysis, factor 2 contributes 9.18% variance and factor 3 contributes 5,16% variance in the given factor analysis. The presence variance for other factors are shown in the table no.3.

Table No-5- Factor Loadings

Varimax Rotated Factor Loadings			
Variable	Factor 1	Factor 2	Factor 3
I am aware that the Holy Gita is a Health Manual	0.591	-0.006	0.127
I know that Lord Krishna is a Psychologist & Counselor	-0.076	0.520	0.243
I have complete Self Awareness about my Health Status	0.424	-0.254	0.185
I have understanding about the 3 types of foods	-0.072	0.554	0.046
My Food affects my Health	-0.057	0.660	-0.125

My Food affects my concentration	-0.236	0.683	-0.099
My Food affects my Studies & Office work	-0.355	0.567	0.004
Satvik Food is the best for life	0.531	-0.047	0.226
I Understand the real meaning of Fasting & its not about only food but controlling the senses	0.191	0.602	-0.079
Fasting of Food is essential for my my good health	-0.353	0.594	0.038
I have complete control over Anger	-0.241	0.639	0.111
Anger affects my health	0.085	0.107	0.552
I have complete control over Lust	0.426	-0.345	0.467
Lust adversely affects my life	0.031	0.069	0.602
I have a lot of Greed in my Life	-0.191	0.563	-0.111
Greed leads to tension and jealousy	0.310	-0.151	0.597
Mental Stress affects my Personal life	-0.026	0.525	-0.097
Yoga & Pranayam helps me to improve life	0.514	-0.073	0.276
I do Pranayam regularly	0.449	-0.312	0.256
My Sleeping schedule is very balanced	0.254	0.429	-0.142
Gymming helps me for Healthy Life	0.181	0.039	0.533
I do workout regularly	0.695	0.034	0.054
I do believe Connecting to myself	0.600	-0.089	0.270
Meditation helps me in being calm and peaceful	0.521	0.004	0.175
I have Fear & Anxiety of future life	0.777	-0.090	0.094
I have fear of death	0.789	-0.135	0.155
I keep on thinking of Past-Present & Future	0.764	-0.092	0.204
My Devotion helps me in Good Mental Health	0.779	-0.146	0.032
Chanting helps positively in my Life	0.626	-0.082	-0.064
I am detached which helps me in my FOCUS	0.776	-0.106	0.084
I believe in Spiritual Healing Thearapies are of great use	0.561	-0.286	0.265
I trust Doctor whom I seek treatment	0.561	-0.128	0.312
Positive Thinking is a good medicine of the mind	0.609	-0.303	0.202
I believe in being Myself and don't get stressed comparing life with others	0.524	-0.232	0.445
Self Confidence helps as boost to my Good health	0.379	-0.281	0.497
Shift in our mindset towards our Spirituality helps in Good Health & Wellness	0.435	-0.251	0.598

Table No-5 shows factor loadings. On one degree of freedom the authors have extracted 35 factors from 36 variables. After verifying reliability and scale of the data factor analysis by using verimax Rotated factor loading is calculated. The Varimax method is the most popular among these techniques and is often used to make principal components analysis (PCA). The

procedure seeks to rotate factors so that the variation of the squared factor loadings for a given factor is made large. From the factor loading following factors extracted.

Factor 1 includes I have fear of death (0.789), My Devotion helps me in Good Mental Health (0.779), I have Fear & Anxiety of future life (0.777), I am detached which helps me in my FOCUS (0.695), I do workout regularly (0.695), Positive Thinking is a good medicine of the mind (0.609), Chanting helps positively in my Life (0.626), I do believe connecting to myself (0.600), I believe in Spiritual Healing Therapies are of great use (0.561), I trust Doctor whom I seek treatment (0.561), I believe in being Myself and don't get stressed comparing life with others(0.524), Meditation helps me in being calm and peaceful (0.521), are showing maximum loadings.

Factor 2 Includes My Food affects my concentration (0.602), My Food affects my concentration (0.683), My Food affects my Health (0.660), I have complete control over Anger (0.639), I have understanding about the 3 types of foods (0.554), Fasting of Food is essential for my my good health (0.594), My Food affects my Studies & Office work (0.567), I know that Lord Krishna is a Psychologist & Counsellor (0.520), I Understand the real meaning of Fasting & its not about only food but controlling the senses (0.602), Determination(0.747), Multitasking (0,700), Need for mentors (0.601) are showing maximum loadings.

Factor 3 Includes Lust adversely affects my life (0.602), Greed leads to tension and jealousy (0.597), Anger affects my health (0.552), Shift in our mindset towards our Spirituality helps in Good Health & Wellness (0.598), Gymming helps me for Healthy Life (0.533) are showing maximum loadings. From the above factor analysis, we perceive that the above-mentioned factors are playing a vital role in Goodness of Health with the help & guidance of Shrimad Bhagavad Gita.

Table No-6

Table No-6 shows screen plot for the given factor analysis. It is observed that after factor-3 shows slope of graph is declining hence. Therefore, plot proposes to stop analysis at the point the mountain ends and the debris (error) begins. In this instance, that point coincides with the Eigen value criterion.

Table No-7

Annova Table

Analysis of Variance					
Source	Type III SS	Df	Mean Sq.	F	Prob.
Model	2628.364	35	75.096	76.650	0.000
Error	5078.897	5184	0.980		
Total	7707.260	5219			

In the Table No-7 researcher has tested hypothesis role of Bhagavad Gita for health problem of working professionals. It is observed that p-value is less than 0.000 hence it rejects null hypothesis and accepts alternative hypothesis i.e. **The Teachings of Shrimad Bhagavad Gita contributes in developing Good health & wellness & also provides solutions to related problems.**

9. Implications of the Gita on Good Health & Wellness Aspects

Freedom from Miseries & Overcoming Sorrow

Fig 1.1

Lord Krishna is the most Eloquent Speaker who has given the most concise solutions to the biggest problems of the life. The problems of life also include problems related to health and wellness issues. In one single shloka of Ch 6 Lord Krishna has given us a masterkey and covered the entire spectrum of both physical and mental good health further leading us to spiritual wellbeing.

*Yuktāhāra-vihārasya yukta-cheṣṭasya karmasu
yukta-svapnāvabodhasya yogo bhavati duḥkha-hā BG 6.17*

Meaning Yukt- Balanced, Aahar-Food, Vihar-Activity, Exercise, Nidra-Sleep, Cheshta-Thoughts, Karm-Duties & Responsibilities. Those who are temperate in eating and recreation, balanced in work, and controlled in sleep, can mitigate all sorrows by practicing Yog.

As a matter of fact the human body is perishable but till the time the human body exists its important for us to make sure that the body is treated as an important resource given to us by the Lord. If the body is fit the mind shall be fit and if the body and mind both are fit our soul also shall be at peace and shall qualify to successfully carry out our day to day actions in life and be one with the higher spirit. Ahar- Shloka on Satvik food, Vihar – recreation, Karma-how to work & Swapna- rest This all leads to good health and we get freedom from miseries .

Fig 1.2

The Dukkha i.e sorrow is adhyatmik which we do face. The Other two types of sorrows are not in our control.

*Duḥkheṣhv-anudvigna-manāḥ sukheṣhu vigata-sprihaḥ
vīta-rāga-bhaya-krodhaḥ sthīta-dhīr munir uchyate BG 2.56*

Meaning -This shloka explains the meaning & root cause of diseases in life. The root cause of illness is the utilization to over utilisation of the indriyas. It speaks of being mentally undisturbed and satisfied in all situations. & we dont crave for pleasure, and we are free from attachment, fear, and anger thus we are on the roadmap of steady wisdom leading to Good health and wellness. Thus one can conclude that for healthy body a healthy mind is a must consisting of these attributes as mentioned in this shloka.

10. Gita and the Dimensions of Good Health

The Gita gives us a holistic understanding of health and also gives a wide range of benefits. We cannot decouple good health from aspects of life which may be social, corporate or spiritual. The holy text defines Health not just Physical wellbeing but also Mental, Emotional, Psychological and Spiritual too. It helps healing us on the level of Mind, Body and Soul. The Gita gives step by step master plan to have a good health, fit mind and body and further realise our self Gain our spiritual health and Be Blissful. Dimensions of Health include physical, mental, social, emotional, spiritual and others. The World Health Organisation (1948) has defined the concept of Health. According to WHO health or good health doesnt just mean one should have no disease, ailments, disabilities or lacunas in the body. It is a holistic concept of an allround good dwelling as a human in terms of a complete physical, mental and social well being too. Gita adds a spiritual dimension which is very important where it states that the human body is the Gift of the God and should be developed so that it can be used to serve the lotus feet of the Lord. Going miles ahead its the holy Gita which highlights the importance and significance of having a Spiritual Master, Guru who shall be Spiritual Guide in our life. In the gym when we learn exercises a Coach or a Trainer is important to us but for the Health and Wellness of our life a qualified Medical Practitioner i.e Doctor is important similarly a bonafide

Guru is also very important who shall impart to us not just how to keep the body, mind and soul fit and fine but also give us transcendental knowledge.

11. Roadmap from the Gita for Good Health and Wellness

The Bhagavad Gita provides us with the following roadmap for achieve our objective of Good Health and Wellness.. The points are discussed in details.

Fig 1.3

1. Diet

*Annādbhavantibhūtāniparjanyādanna-sambhavaḥ
yajñād bhavati parjanyo yajñāḥ karma-samudbhavaḥ BG 3.14*

Meaning -Gita states that all the living organisms are evolved from food they eat and food comes from rain. All of them are dependent on food which is grown only if there are good rains . The rains occur from the performance of sacrifice and the when we do our prescribed duties then sacrifice happens.

*Ahāras tv api sarvasya tri-vidho bhavati priyaḥ
yajñas tapas tathā dānam teṣhām bhedaṃ imaṃ śhṛiṇu BG 17.7*

Meaning- For existence of human beings food is an integral part and need and preference of food is based on dispositions which are true based on the charity, austerity and sacrifice. The Gita which blesses us with all round happiness also provides us divine guidelines about food. Gita will help us Innerly and keep us fit naturally from inside making our life “ Tushyantich Ramantich” The Gita classifies food and diet also into 3 categories , The Right type of Food is as follows –

Satwik Food : BG 17.8

*Ayuḥ-sattva-balārogya-sukha-prīti-vivardhanāḥ
rasyāḥ snigdhaḥ sthīrā hṛidyā āhārāḥ sāttvika-priyāḥ BG 17.8*

Meaning -Vegetarian food is the mode of goodness and should be pure, illuminating & serene create a sense of happiness and satisfaction Such foods promote longetivity and bestow good health, virtue, happiness and satisfaction.They are juicy, naturally tasteful,mild and beneficial. These include grains, pulses, beans,fruits, vegetables,milk and other vegetarianism foods. There are conducive for Spiritual Life.

Rajsik Food 17.9

*Kaṭv-amlā-lavaṇāṭy-uṣhṇa- tīkṣhṇa-rūkṣha-vidāhinaḥ
āhārā rājasasyeṣṭhā duḥkha-śhokāmaya-pradāḥ BG 17.9*

Meaning -The food which is too bitter,saulty,chillies,sugar are rajasik . They can create results of illhealth,agitation and disappointments This type of food is consumed by those who Eat to live and not live to eat.Those in the mode of goodness find them disgusting and so wont prefer Satvik food only.

Tamsik Food 17.10

*Yāta-yāmaṁ gata-rasaṁ pūti paryuṣhitaṁ cha yat
uchchhiṣṭam apī chāmedhyaṁ bhojanaṁ tāmāsa-priyam BG 17.10*

Meaning -Stale,Tasteless,Putrid,Poluted,Spoiled,left over,impure ,food cooked more than 3 hours is called as Tamsik food.This includes more of non vegetarian stuff. The mind and body impact to each other the food influences human nature.The “Chaadopya Upanishad” explains that the core part of the food we eat passes out as feces. The subtle part of the food becomes flesh and the subtlest part becomes mind.We should be able to connect to the Infinite Energy of the Universe! If we want to develop your personality then the food should be balanced.Timing of the food is also important .Lunch should be before afternoon and dinner should be before night. 50% of good health can be achieved only by eating right food at right time. We should eat atleast 20 minutes chewing nicely. Butter milk and curd should be taken only in the afternoon and not in the night.

The Essence of life is “Jathragni” (Digestive Fire)

*Yajña-śhiṣṭāśhinaḥsantomuchyantesarva-kilbiṣhaiḥ
bhuñjate te tvagham pāpā ye pachantyātma-kāraṇāt BG 3.13*

Meaning -The food which we eat needs to be offered as a sacrifice to the Lord and so we should pray before we eat. The food which we take is not just food but the Prasad of the Lord which comes after the sacrifice. Many people cook and eat food for their enjoyment this is too low level thinking. But we must cook food as a Prasad,offer it too the Lord as a sacrifice and consume the food as a Prasad with love and mindfulness. Thus this food also has to be satvik food.

*Aham vaiśhvānaro bhūtvā prāṇinām deham āśhritaḥ
prāṇāpāna-samāyuktaḥ pachāmy annam chatur-vidham BG 15.14*

Meaning- The Lord says that he is the form of the fire which digests food in the stomach of all living entities in form of “Vaishvanaro” Based on the same there are 4 types of Foods.Bhojya : Chewable Eg breadPeya : Liquid, Drinkable, Swalloble E.g Milk, Juice,Koshya : Suckable Eg Sugarcane Leh : Lickable Eg Honey.Keeping our inner flame burning bright through diet.. According to ancient wisdom we have to be our own mini-sun also known as “Jathragni” within us. We can protect and balance Inner agni via proper consumption of food and drinks in the right quantities and at the right times, keeping the seasonal effects of food in our mind.

2.Fasting

*Satataṁkīrtayantomāmyatantaśhchadriḍha-vratāḥ
namasyantaśh cha mām bhaktyā nitya-yuktā upāsate BG 9.14*

Meaning -Lord Krishna here states the worshipping by “Dhridh Vrata” i.e Great determination. Fasting is one of the austerities which is considered as a part the worship of the Lord. Our body is like a machine and machine needs some rest and servicing for its maintainance.For the same there is a provision of fasting given by rishi munis. Fasting is also a part of austerity . Ekadashi fasting once in 15 days helps in good health . The Theory of “Autophagy”i.e fasting is a process wherein human body eats its own damaged cells and unused proteins.If there is no periodical fasting there could be accumulation of damaged cells which can lead to health issues so fasting as per capacity is recommended. In Indian culture there is recommendation of fasting at various important occasions including a fortnightly fast of Ekadashi which is higly helpful in repairing the damaged cells and maintaining the system of good health by giving the required mental,physical strength , cleansing and rest to the body.

3. Sleeping

*Nātyaśhnatastuyogostinachaikāntamanaśhnataḥ
na chāti-svapna-śhīlasya jāgrato naiva chārjuna BG 6.16*

Meaning -There has to be balancing in sleep and waking up . Excess sleep and less sleep both are not advisable. Gita teaches us that Sleep is a Goddess ie Nidra Devi. Sleeping and waking this continues till our earthly existence Sleep is the backbone of good health .It gives us energy and helps in our fitness. Our sleep is affected by various factors and so disturbed sleep creates health issues for us. Here again requirement of sleep of Baby and Adult sleep differs.Many people use alarm but actually alarm spoils are our energy.

4. Breathing

*Apāne juhvati prāṇam prāṇe 'pānam tathāpare
prāṇāpāna-gatī ruddhvā prāṇāyāma-parāyaṇāḥ*

*apare niyataharah pranana praneshu juhvati
sarve 'pyete yajna-vido yajna-kshapita-kalmashah BG 4.29*

Meaning -Our breath is the most important lifeline of our life and Gita guides us on the aspect of breathing also. When we are angry breath reduces, calmness leads to good breathing and improves our mind. Our thoughts are proportional to our breadth says 'Hathyogaprapita".Slow your breadth and slow your thoughts. This is possible by Pranayama . There is so much importance of Pranayama mentioned in the Bhagavad Gita .*Gita adhyanasya sheelasy pranayam parasyacha naiv santi hi paapani purvajanmakrutanicchha* 'says Adi Shankaracharya in the Holy "Gita Mahatmyam".The person is instant in reading Gita and does pranayam instantly his or her sins of the past birth will be washed out. Lord Krishna, strongly propagates Pranayama-the 4th practice of Ashtanga yoga as a powerful way to cleanse the impurities of mind, body and soul. Relax your mind, detoxify by pranayam. This comes as the 4th practice of the "Ashtang Yog". It is observed that Pranayama increases the application of a mental willpower and alertness of an individual which helps realose his dreams and vision. Pranayam helps us in being emotionally stronger and eliminating stress from the mind and body. Amongst all the sacrifices Krishna has also asked us to sacrifice the breath i.e learning to control the breathing. The same should be ideally done in the morning. Pranayam will help us in both our physical fitness , mental well being, material upliftment and spiritual advancement too ! People doing pranayama will be benefitted by stronger will power, fit body and positive thinking with a greater level of self confidence. Pranayam helps in keeping the mind,calm,stable and positive focused towards our goals, dreams ,vision and mission of life.

There are 5 Airs as follows-

Pran – Heart, Apan –Excretory air, Samaan-Heat, Vyan-Light,Vaat , Bal body, Udaan- Bal Head & Body.

Sub airs – naag, Kum-Blinking , Yawning etc.

Praana – Life expectancy, Life Span based on “karma”. Increases our life span.Krishna says I am the Wind which purifies our mind and body. When we do deep breathing and pranyama we throw out toxic thoughts.. We say dont get on my nerves. There are many kinds of Pranayama and breathing techniques.

Shri Shri Ravishankar Founder of Art Of Living has designed “Sudarshan Kriya” which has taught a different way of breathing. Swami Ramdev has also introduced different types of Pranayam and is sweeping the globe based on his breathing techniques, “Triangular Breathing Techniques” ,”Kriya Yoga” by Paramhans Yoga Nanda. With Pranyama the disturbing thoughts in our mind are deleted and our mind feels less burden and toxic thoughts which create stress are thrown out of the body. The residual thoughts will decrease and focused thoughts will increase with the Pranayama.

5.Benefits of Meditation

*Yuñjannevaṃsadātmānaṃyogīniyata-mānaśaḥ
śhāntim nirvāṇa-paramām mat-sansthām adhigachchhati BG 6.15*

Meaning –The Best way of meditation is to constantly keeping the mind absorbed in the lotus feet of the Lord and become a Yogi. Such a Yogi with discipline attains liberation and attains supreme peace. This is the Best type of Meditation.This helps to keep the mind calm and take right decisions.. Daily meditation helps in getting joy no problem seems to big. For being self motivated and self driven its important we meditate daily . There is a lot of internal dirt in the mind and also the mental fat. Meditation can help in the inner cleansing. It releases sin,increases memory power, taking right decisions, clarity of thought and clarity of intellect, better functioning of brain, smoother functioning of thoughts. Meditation helps and benefits in Mind control, increasing fearlessness ,handle situations positively,changes our attitude towards life and also develops our positive responses to adversity and crisis management..

6.Conquering the Fear Factor

*Abhayaṃsattva-sanśhuddhirjñāna-yoga-vyavasthitih
dānaṃ damaśh cha yajñāśh cha svādhyāyas tapa ārjavam BG 16.1*

Meaning-Lord Krishna advises us to stay connected to the divine and bring in fearlessness in ourselves. He also states in the below shloka that a person surrendering to him need not fear and leave everything upto him.

*Sarva-dharmān parityajya mām ekaṁ śharaṇaṁ vraja
ahaṁ tvām sarva-pāpebhyo mokṣhayiṣhyāmi mā śhuchaḥ BG 18.66*

Meaning -Arjuna was in the state of panic and Lord Krishna teaches the Bhagavad Gita to Arjuna to remove his fear and panic. Fearness the first sign of illness. Fearlessness is the first requirement of success The only cause of success is Fearlessness and Confidence. For Eg Dhruva he walked fearlessly in the forest. Based on your desire, Universe connects you, we all are connected to the Universe. Very intricate network is there in Universe.

7. Gita & Metaphysical Concept :Overcome fear of death

*Dehino 'smin yathā dehe kaumāraṁ yauvanaṁ jarā
tathā dehāntara-prāptir dhīras tatra na muhyati BG 2.13*

Meaning -The souls passes from one body to another body in a new life .The wise are not deluded by this.

*Vāsānsi jīrṇāni yathā vihāyanavāni grīhṇāti naro 'parāṇi
tathā śharīrāṇi vihāya jīrṇānya nyāni sanyāti navāni dehī BG 2.22*

Meaning -Its like a person changes his own clothes and wears new clothes similarly the soul gets a new body. We all who have come on planet earth wether humans and animals will have to leave our bodies and one day move on This is inevitable Gita teaches us not to fear death at all and understand the true meaning of life and death. Its the system of nature which is beautiful. The five elements of material body merge with the eternal elements of the nature. By fearing about death we will only spoil our death . By fearing our death one cannot avoid death. So the best thing to do as per Gita is understand death and treat it as something divine and accept the same as a process of change which is integral. Nothing is immortal, nobody is permanent here we all are temporary. The Biggest lesson which Gita teaches us is the immortality of the soul , the nectar of Atman(soul) which leads to a spiritual lifestyle based on the wonderful and mystic theory of metaphysical science. Thus for achieving good health and mental wellness one must stop worrying and must not fear about death.

8. Physical exercises

*Niyataṁ kuru karma tvam karma jyāyo hyakarmaṇaḥ
śharīra-yātrāpi cha te na prasiddhyed akarmaṇaḥ BG 3.8*

Meaning -Physical fitness is an important requirement of our daily life and it can be achieved by regularly work out and physical exercises Swami Vivekananda much emphasized the same in his philosophy and stated that we should read football , work out , build our muscles and then read the Gita. Once there is good blood circulation in our body and we are fit we shall be in a better position and our mind shall be more focused to understand the Gita and the teachings of

Lord Krishna in a much better way. This doesn't mean that playing football or doing exercise is a prerequisite for reading the Gita, but by doing so one would feel fresh and have a good blood circulation that would help to understand the Gita by much concentration and focus. By skipping such daily activities of exercise there would be depreciation of the body and maintaining the physical fitness will also become difficult. Let's treat physical exercise as our "Niyatam karma" i.e. obligatory duty and lead towards Good Health & wellness! Some people may not be able to get good health without exercises.

9. The Sense of Surrender & Devotion as a Cure for Health problems & disorder

*Māmchayovyabhichāreṇabhakti-yogenasevate
sa guṇān samatīyaitān brahma-bhūyāya kalpate BG 14.26*

Meaning – Those who serve the lotus feet of the Lord with single minded devotion rise above the modes of the material nature and rise at the highest level of Spiritual status i.e. Brahman. The above shlokas give us a divine guideline from the Lord that the sense of surrender & devotion has its own strength like the medical treatment. The best solution is to Connect to Krishna, Love the Krishna More, Remember the Lord more and his love for us, fix mind on the Lord. Through Chanting, Bhajan, Music, Philosophy, Darshan of deities. **Making Krishna the anchor of the innerworld thus the agitation of inner world reduces.** Medical treatment is a must in case of clinical requirements but Stigmatization should be avoided. Wherever needed medication is a must and it should not be avoided. Only Spiritual practices can't be the medicine or substitute to the medicine to our health issues. Spiritual is the director of the material. Arjuna used the spiritual knowledge of Gita directed it in the material knowledge and led himself to success in the war. Spiritual enables us to direct the material constructively. Arjuna won the war of Kurukshetra with the SKILLS and competencies he had since years gained by his hard work and penance & the WILL given by the knowledge/wisdom of Gita! In US anti-depressant is among the top 5 selling drugs now. The solutions are much more pathologised and much marketing is done on the medicines as the research production is less. Then what's the solution? The Lord says those who are devoted to him do rise above all the three gunas so can rise above all mind and body related miseries too. Transcending the three modes of material nature are very important to get free from the miseries of life and move towards Godhead which is the final objective of human life. Krishna says Our Basic Nature cannot be changed, our Swadharma i.e. a mind of Kshatriya cannot be Brahman. Spiritual and material ones it comes to mind – it has to be dealt with utmost care and carefully dealt. Some aspects of Mind can be cured, healed, refined, changed, purified, reformed some aspects need to be changed. Lust, Anger, Greed & the 6 'ripus' can be changed, minimized, reduced and further can be channelized and have to be cured spiritually. When we fight a war, we do whatever we require to do so that it works out for us, use it, make it work and continue our service to Lord Krishna.

10. Control the Senses

*Ye hi sansparśha-jā bhogā duḥkha-yonaya eva te
ādyantavantaḥ kaunteya na teṣhu ramate budhaḥ BG 5.22*

Meaning -The senses of our body are the channels and source all the worldly pleasures. It's important that we control them and put necessary break and regulation otherwise it shall take us to many health issues. Pleasure arising from contact with sense objects that appearing enjoyable to worldly minded people are the source of misery ,such pleasures have beginning and end and so the wise do not have delight in them. The senses naturally keep experiencing attachment to the sense objects, but do not be controlled by them, for they are way-layers and foes. A person should not become infatuated by the temptations and pleasures of the senses.

11. Management of Anger, Lust & Greed

*Tri-vidhaṃ narakasyedaṃ dvāraṃ nāśhanam ātmanaḥ
kāmaḥ krodhas tathā lobhas tasmād etat trayam tyajet BG 16.21*

Meaning- The Gita says that there are There are three gates leading to the hell of self-destruction for the soul—lust, anger, and greed. Therefore we all should abandon these three. Anger is a negative trait of which we all should resist ourselves from .Anger leads to clouding of judgment, which results in bewilderment of the memory. When the memory is bewildered, the intellect gets destroyed; and when the intellect is destroyed, one is ruined. So Krishna says to control anger and overcome the same without which good health is not possible. Thus overcoming anger, lust and greed shall lead to good health of a human being.

12. Trust the Right Doctor

*kārpaṇya-doṣhopahata-svabhāvaḥ, pṛichchhāmi tvām dharma-sammūḍha-chetāḥ
yach- chhreyah syānniśchitam brūhi tanme, śhiṣhyaste 'ham śhādhi mām tvām prapannam*

BG 2.7

Meaning -Arjuna trusted Krishna surrendered to him and followed each and every instruction and prescription given by Krishna. For surrendering himself Arjuna became the student of Krishna. Here it clearly indicates that we need to trust the Doctor who we are seeking treatment. And most importantly to achieve good health we should follow the prescription of medicines within the time schedule and also observe all the abstinence told by the Doctor. Good health and bodily vigor also depend upon the purity of the remedial measure taken by us. The Doctor whom we visit and we take treatment we must trust the Doctor, his diagnosis, his prescription and his medicines the way Arjuna did.

13. Work on Ourselves & Our Strengths

Shreyān swa-dharmo viguṇaḥ para-dharmāt sv-anuṣṭhitāt

swa-dharme nidhanam śhreyah para-dharmo bhayāvahaḥ BG 3.35

Meaning - In the above three shlokas Gita time and again reminds us to follow our “Swadharma” and Be Yourself. It is essential to work hard on our naturally blessed abilities and follow our own path, this shall give us more mental stability. For peace of mind we need to operate on the basis of natural tendencies and set up and set up according to our nature. But for being ourselves we need to aim to be faultless. For being faultless we need to work correcting our mistakes of the past and need to have control on our senses else they will take us for a ride. We need to work on our strengths and not get bogged down by the weakness rather overcome them. Many people in this world don't live their own life and try to live some other persons dreams and convictions. In addition they have a habit of comparing their life with others and keep feeling jealous or distressed because of the success of others too. This syndrome of comparison and the imitation of others leads to much complications and further leads to both mental and consequently physical health issues. The concept of Swadharma also means doing your own duties. Everyone wants to copy things sometimes we want to use shortcuts. But the fact is one must be able to do things “naturally” and for the same we must Be Ourselves and for being Ourselves one should firstly understand our “Swadharma”.

14. Gita & Self Health Awareness

Kṣhetra-jñāṁ chāpi mām viddhi sarva-kṣhetreṣhu bhārata

kṣhetra-kṣhetrajñāyor jñānam yat taj jñānam mataṁ mama BG 13.3

Meaning - The Lord says to Arjuna that he is the knower of all fields of activities. He proclaims that he understands the body as field of activities, the soul and God as the knowers of the field which the Lord holds as true knowledge. Many of us don't know about our Body completely. Body has material components which has physical structure and organs and spiritual components which includes souls and super soul . If we know about God and the Supreme personality of the Godhead the divine knowledge of the Gita will help us about knowing everything about our Self ,our mind,body, soul and shall solve our own problems. Happiness is much easier for a spiritual, religious person. For leading a happy and healthy life we must try to follow the religious principles. How to know ? Its not mentioned in any material book. Its mentioned in Gita ..

15. Bhagavad Gita Techniques for Managing Emotions

Indriyāṇi parāṇyāhur indriyebhyaḥ param manaḥ

manasas tu parā buddhir yo buddheḥ paratas tu saḥ BG 3.42

Meaning -Our human body is comprised of faculties. They senses are greater than the body . Mind is greater than the senses . More greater is the intellect and then the soul. The Atman! Gita provides us with the heavenly information on the Atman !

The Gita shows multiple techniques for managing emotions.

- 1 .Meditation
2. Contemplation.
3. Surrendering & Offering (Yajna)
4. Shifting ones attitude.
5. Developing a larger perspective about self,others,universe and divine.
6. Being a witness to ones body and mind commonly knows as mindfulness.(Sakshi, Khetragya)

Just –Let-Go

Non attachment & Psychological Flexibility.

Another factor which has been given some importance is the capacity to have healthy separation and an ability to let go things. A lot of pain and suffering is due to being attached to something which one is not able to let go !Eg The Monkeys hand get stuck in Pot. See the Self as consciousness (self as context) distance yourself from the thoughts (cognitive diffusion) This is an idea running across Bhagavad Gita. Awe & Revenence Ch 9-11 describes feeling of awe,when you are devoted to do something higher than yourself you will feel awe & reverence.ie Bhaktiyog . It may also trigger awe for a reader. Multiple shlokas in Gita are devoted to positive qualities with cultivating from persistence to friendliness and compassion etc. (Daivi Sampada, Satwik Gunas)These qualities studied extensively in Positive Psychology-found to be associated with the basic ingredients of positive mental health. (Eg Positive emotions , Engagement, meaning, positive relationships & accomplishments) They are as follows Perspective, Bravery, Persistence, Honesty, Zest Kindness,Team Work,Forgiveness,Capacity to love & be loved, Fairness, Leadership, Forgiveness. Gita is a treasure for innumerable psychological insights. It may enhance mental helath through many pathways.Time has come to increasily build mental health Intervention based on these insights. Bhagavad Gita helps in emotional part of Parkinson. Counseling & Psychotherapy intense required.

The Gitas Two Point Superb Formula for Success & Wellness

Śhrībhagavānvācha

Asanśhayam mahā-bāhomanodurnigrahāṃchalam

abhyāsenā tu kaunteya vairāgyeṇa cha grihyate BG 6.35

Meaning -

1. Abhyas : Practice with consistent efforts, pull your mind back and dedicate your mind to the holy name and devotional services of the Lord.
2. Vairagya : Detachment from those things which are not pleasing to the Lord. Detachment from matter and attachment from the spirit.

Our effort should be to pull back our mind from all the crazy things and focus on things we should be supposed to focus. Eventually it will get submissive and controlled like the way the Lion is controlled by the ring master in the circus. The mind is like a wild animal if its put in a cage it will grow crazy and hit the cage hard and further will become submissive. Then it wont roar. This is the time when the mind has to be captured. Krishna further has suggested the Process of chanting and also keeping the mind engaged in 9 types of devotional services of the Lord. Keep remembering Krishna I,e “Smaranam”.

The Significance & Benefit of Gita acknowledged by Medical Science

The Teachings of the Gita are now no longer only the matter of faith and worship but it has also been acknowledged and accepted by the Medical Science and the Experts in the field as well.

1. Research has proved that “Divine Word can defeat Diabetes” The Team of researchers including Doctors from Osmania General Hospital (OGH) has found a “Spiritual way of healing DIABETES” and the source is “Shrimad Bhagavad Gita. The divine shlokas of the Gita are actually addressed to various situations in life and helps in promoting positive coping skills which overcome illness..

2. The study published in Indian Journal of Endocrinology and Metabolism had doctors and researchers drawn all across within India and abroad which derives that the Gita shlokas are more than religious or philosophical context. For a diabetes patient change in lifestyle, restraints, complying medical advice self monitoring of blood glucose and insulin administration which are not well perceived by much patients need motivation too. This is where the Gita comes in picture. It tries to eliminate negative mood such as grief and anger. The Gita helps to reduce counter regulatory hormone levels by promoting calmness of mind. This calmness and relaxation of mind is a pre-requisite of diabetes management. The blood sugar level cant be achieved until and unless the mind of the patient is calm and stable. The Beauty of the Teachings of the Gita is that Lord Krishna along with the Divine Knowledge of the Soul insists in maintenance of stability of mind through meditation and also good physical fitnesss through exercise, change in food habits and improving life style.

3. World renowned neurosurgeon Dr Premanand Ramani along with prescribing medicines also teaches the Importance of Gita shlokas to his patients. He insists that if we read Gita carefully properly and follow it correctly most of the ailments will disappear This itself is an evidence that Medical practioners today have accepted the Importance of Lord Krishna’s divine words as also

a medicine for physical and mental diseases. The Gita has given regulatory advice to the human beings on Life Style, Eating Habits, Overcoming stress and clear guidelines on Life Style Management !

4. In the recent times the world faced a challenge and havoc of Covid Pandemic. Covid was seen to be more destructive for those who had previous ailments or those who did not have regulated lifestyle. By following the principles of the Bhagavad Gita we can have a disease free life and regulated life defeating the Covid Problem.

Conclusion & Results

Bhagavad Gita thus provides all the master keys as to how we can achieve a healthy body and healthy mind for a happy life. Its important that we achieve and establish ourselves in the right consciousness To be happy means to actually accept the reality of life however it is. This shall protect us from all sort of depression and help us in maintaining our good mental health. We should understand that life offers us various situations but we should note that Being Happy is a Choice ! For our mental fitness we should count our blessings God has given us body we should know how to use the body . Lets become Pandavas for a Happy and Healthy life !Internal Qualities – Will lead to good work,good health,success comes and follows back wealth comes. Stable mind and success . Gita is complex if we don't have a right guide and we may not understand.E.g Trains at a glance. The survey conducted amongst the working executives of the Corporate world and the statistical analysis of their responses clearly reflects that there is an deeper impact of Gita teachings and its following on Good Health and Fitness factor.Gita leads us from illness to wellness and the Good Mental & Physical health is a MUST for Good work life . We should clearly understand that Mind,Body,Soul is given by Krishna and material pleasures are also given by Krishna so it has to be used for the right purpose , achieve Work Excellence and finally moving towards our ultimate Goal of Krishna Consciousness.

Information of Compliance with ethical standards

1. Funding: This is a self-funded research undertaken by the co-researchers themselves. No other research consultancy, company or agency has funded the research.
2. Competing interest: The authors hereby declare that we don't have any competing interest with anybody for any reason or any purpose through this research paper.
3. Human and Animal Rights: This article does not contain any studies with animals performed by any of the authors.
4. Informed Consent: Informed consent was obtained from all the resources, participants and individuals who were included in the study of the research paper.

Limitations of the Study

The study gives a detailed analysis the responses of executives on Impact of Gita teachings on health and wellness It reflects the statistics of how many working executives do know & follow Gita philosophy actually in maintaining good health . The Study has been limited only to Mumbai & Navi Mumbai region and a greater geographical region and bigger population model can be considered .

Scope for Future Research

The further study should be more comprehensive and specific statistical models can be designed based on quantitative analysis. A Health and wellness framework, Fitness matrix based on Gita can be designed. The research covered generalized population from multiple sectors, Further narrowed down research can be conducted for specific sectors and especially for the Leadership bandwidth. . A specialized study and research on this subject can be conducted and a “Wellness Plan” can be presented to the Corporates based on Gita.

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